

Supporting Information Text S2: DigitAF survey (WP3 – Task 3.3) – Biodiversity & Overall respondent characteristics

*: Multiple answers possible

Overall characteristics of a survey respondents

- 1) I confirm that I have read and understand the information provided on this form and give my consent to taking part in this research.
 - a. **Accept/Decline**
 - 2) Please indicate if this response is part of the testing process or if it's the actual response you wish to give to the questions.
 - a. **"Test" answer/Actual answer**
 - 3) Please enter your personal code below. This was previously assigned to you by DigitAF staff.
 - 4) Please select your age?
 - a. **18-35 years old**
 - b. **36-50 years old**
 - c. **51-65 years old**
 - d. **66+ years old**
 - e. **Prefer not to say**
 - 5) What is your gender?
 - a. **Male**
 - b. **Female**
 - c. **Other**
 - d. **Prefer not to say**
 - 6) In which countries do you carry out your business or activities?
 - 7) What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 - a. **No formal education**
 - b. **Secondary school (up to 16y old)**
 - c. **High school (up to 18y old)**
 - d. **Bachelor's degree or equivalent**
 - e. **Master's degree or equivalent**
 - f. **Doctoral or above**
 - 8) What type of stakeholder are you?
 - a. **Farmer and/or landowner**
 - b. **Farm advisor**
 - c. **Policymaker**
 - d. **Stakeholder in the value chain**
 - e. **Researcher**
 - f. **...**
 - 9) Please indicate the size of your farm in ha?
 - 10) What is your farm type?*&ol style="list-style-type: none;"> - a. **Arable**
 - b. **Horticulture (vegetables)**
 - c. **Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine)**
 - d. **Mixed (Livestock + Crops)**
 - e. **Livestock (Pigs)**
 - f. **Livestock (Poultry)**
 - g. **Livestock (Beef and sheep)**
 - h. **Livestock (Dairy)**
 - i. **Agroforestry**
 - j. **Forestry**
 - k. **Agri-tourism and education**
 - l. **Organic**
 - m. **...**
- 11) What types of farm do you advise?*&ol style="list-style-type: none;">- a. **Arable**
- b. **Horticulture (vegetables)**
- c. **Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine)**
- d. **Mixed (Livestock + Crops)**
- e. **Livestock (Pigs)**
- f. **Livestock (Poultry)**
- g. **Livestock (Beef and sheep)**
- h. **Livestock (Dairy)**
- i. **Agroforestry**
- j. **Forestry**
- k. **Agri-tourism and education**
- l. **Organic**
- m. **...**
- 12) Do you also have a secondary stakeholder role?
ex. you're a farmer but you're also a researcher
 - a. **Yes, Farmer and/or landowner**
 - b. **Yes, Farm advisor**
 - c. **Yes, Policymaker**
 - d. **Yes, Stakeholder in the value chain**
 - e. **Yes, Researcher**
 - f. **No, I do not have a secondary stakeholder role**

Biodiversity

PA: Questions included for policy actors (all the questions are asked to farmers and advisors)

The importance of biodiversity and its assessment

The primary target of agriculture is the production of consumable food, however, agricultural practices can lend additional benefits as habitat for numerous of species and benefit biodiversity as such.

Alas, the past decades, a severe decline in agriculture-related biodiversity was observed. Hence there is a lot of research going on to assess biodiversity properly in agricultural systems.

With biodiversity we here mean all species groups (plants, birds, insects, mammals, ...) that occur in or around agricultural fields and that are likely to be affected by agroforestry practices. We perform this survey to investigate the desires and interests of the stakeholders that can make use of our research.

- 1) How important do you consider biodiversity in agroecosystems? PA
 - a. Likert scale (Not at all important/Somewhat important/Neutral/important/Very important)
- 2) Do you know any biodiversity assessment models or tools (software to quantify biodiversity)? PA
 - a. Yes/No
- 3) If yes, which ones? PA
- 4) Do you think a model or tool predicting biodiversity in agroforestry would be useful? PA

This tool could be used to enter the specifications of a field/farm and would give as an output a proxy for biodiversity under these circumstances.

 - a. Likert scale (Not at all important/Somewhat important/Neutral/important/Very important)
 - i. → exclude users that answer 'not important?'
- 5) Briefly explain why? PA

Specifics and relevance of an agroforestry-based biodiversity tool

- 6) Which output would you expect from a biodiversity model or tool? * PA
 - a. An overall score for total biodiversity on the farm/field
 - b. A score for several specific species groups (e.g. birds, mammals, insects, plants, ...)
 - c. A proxy for biodiversity effects generated by implementing agroforestry elements
 - d. Proposed actions (e.g. hedgerow planting) to increase biodiversity on the farm/field
 - e. ...
- 7) If you chose 'A score for several specific species groups (e.g. birds, mammals, insects, plants, soil fauna, pollinators, ...) biodiversity' in the previous question: which species groups would have preference and why? * PA

(Add as many as you desire on separate lines.)
- 8) What do you think is the optimal scale for a biodiversity tool? * PA
 - a. Plot/field level (one field within a farm)
 - b. Farm level (all the land managed within a farm (e.g. also includes small forests patches))
 - c. Landscape level (beyond, large area with all streams, woodlands, pastures, cropland, villages ...)
 - d. ...
- 9) What amount of time per year are you willing to invest in biodiversity assessment?
 - a. (hours) : (minutes)
- 10) What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment tool?

The current management of the farm/field.

 - a. Yes/No/Maybe

The amount of trees (and tree species) on the farm/field.

 - b. Yes/No/Maybe

Some easy to record and charismatic species (e.g. birds).

 - c. Yes/No/Maybe
- 11) What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment tool?

*Other ideas? **

The tool-design

12) How should the tool be constructed?

PA

- a. Based only on publicly available maps
- b. Based on a checklist of the current management and status of the farm/field
- c. A mixed approach
- d. ...

13) What kind of tool would you like to use? *

PA

- a. Website on the internet
- b. Freely available computer program
- c. QGIS/arcGIS-tool (software to handle maps)
- d. Excel spreadsheet
- e. R program (software for data-analysis)
- f. ...

The validation of the tool

After a theoretical construction of any tool, it is important to validate the outputs with real data. This ensures that the tool really is a good option to be used as proxy. If the validation data shows a different pattern, changes in the tool are desired.

In this section, we would like to ask what species groups you think are relevant or are you interested in to validate the tool?

14) What species groups do you think are relevant or are you interested in to validate the tool? *

PA

- a. Plants
- b. Birds
- c. Bats
- d. Other mammals
- e. Butterflies
- f. Pollinators (e.g. bees, bumblebees, ...)
- g. Spiders
- h. Other arthropods
- i. Amphibians & reptiles
- j. Moths
- k. Mushrooms
- l. Soil fauna (e.g. woodlice, millipedes, nematodes, ...)
- m. Earthworms
- n. ...

Agroforestry-perception

1) Which of the following practices do you associate with agroforestry? *

- a. Biodynamic orchard
- b. Wood pasture
- c. Alley cropping
- d. Hedges
- e. Regenerative farming
- f. Grazed orchard and woodland
- g. Shelterbelts and windbreak
- h. Kitchen gardens
- i. Riparian buffer strips
- j. Dehesa and montado
- k. Silvopastoral system
- l. Silvoarable system
- m. Farm woodlands
- n. Short-rotation coppice
- o. Increasing tree cover on farm
- p. Forest gardening
- q. ... (none of the above)